

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 1.2: Intermediate report on activity

1st October 2022

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 - 5.1.3.** *Dissemination and communication activities and number of people in theses activities (EITHE 17.1)*
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 - 5.3. Contribution to the mandatory Core EIT KPIs**

¹ Please fill in the contribution table including all of the mandatory Core EIT KPIs in chapter 5.3

1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims at applying the principles of the New European Bauhaus to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to describe the initial outputs of the project according to the submitted work plan, as well as the identification of potential risks and mitigation measures. One of the initial outputs is the definition of the co-creation methodology to be applied during all the events planned by the project. Moreover, further initial outputs resulted from the activities implemented during four participatory events held from July to September 2022 in Arsoli.

2. The overall progress of the activity

2.1. Brief description of the activity, main challenges

In this sub-section, a brief description of the realized activities according to the work plan is described.

Activity A1 – Management: the financial, administrative, and technical activities have been carried out. The data management plan (DMP) (Del.1.1) and the intermediate report (Del.1.2) have been provided.

Activity A2 – Target group identification, and need analysis: during the open day event organized on July 29th, 2022, the first step of the co-creation of the social farm for the extraction of needs and ideas has been performed. The expected deliverables (Del.2.1 and 2.2) illustrating the call for participation and summarizing the results of the event have been provided. The call for participation in the open day event is shown below.

 IRPPS Istituto di Ricerche
sulla Popolazione
e le Politiche Sociali con il patrocinio del
Comune di Arsoli eit Community
New European Bauhaus

**INVITO A PARTECIPARE ALL'EVENTO DI
LANCIO del PROGETTO SOCIAL4FOOD**

**Ti piace stare a contatto con la natura e vuoi contribuire a
tramandare la tradizione della fagiolina arsolana?**

**Unisciti a noi per apprendere le pratiche di coltivazione e di
cucina della fagiolina**

**Partecipa ai nostri laboratori collaborativi e contribuisci
anche tu alla realizzazione di un orto sociale**

**TI ASPETTIAMO IL
29 LUGLIO 2022
presso il TEATRO COMUNALE**

**dalle ore 11 alle ore 13: ATTIVITA' per gli
ADOLESCENTI (13-18 anni) e ADULTI**
**dalle ore 16.30 alle ore 17.30: ATTIVITA' per
BAMBINI 8-12 anni**

SOCIAL4FOOD è un progetto ideato dal CNR-IRPPS e finanziato dalla
Comunità Europea volto a migliorare il contatto tra le giovani generazioni e
gli spazi pubblici verdi, guidati dalla saggezza degli anziani. Attraverso una
serie di attività di agricoltura sociale, il progetto mira a stimolare il
coinvolgimento dei bambini e degli adolescenti arsolani (compresi anche i
giovani immigrati) nella coltivazione e nella cucina collaborativa della
"fagiolina arsolana".

The open day event represents the first phase of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach. Four different target groups, including local teenagers, local children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers, have been engaged in an attempt to identify experiences and ideas on the growing and cooking of the fagiolina arsolana. Specifically, two different sessions were organized to meet the needs of the different target groups: the former for adults and adolescents and the latter for children. In the first session, dedicated to adults and adolescents, the world café method was applied that consisted of the following activities: collection of experiences, elicitation of ideas, sharing of ideas, and voting of ideas. In the second section, dedicated to children, the storytelling method was applied that consisted of the following activities: storytelling of experiences with emotion definition, collection of tips, and drawings. The results of the discussion allowed to collect experiences on the growing and cooking of the fagiolina arsolana and needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm.

Activity A3 – Co-creation methodology definition: the co-creation methodology has been defined and the expected deliverable (Del.3.1) has been provided. The co-creation methodology is based on the design thinking approach which is a non-linear, iterative process that provides a solution-based approach to solving problems. More details are provided in Section 2.2.

Activity A4 – SOCIAL4FOOD training activities set up, implementation: SOCIAL4FOOD training activities were organized. Specifically, the green social laboratories took place on August 18th 2022 and September 24th 2022, the SOCIAL4FOOD competition on September 4th 2022, and the second step of the co-design of the social farm on September 24th 2022. These events constituted the second phase of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach. Four different target groups have been involved including local teenagers, local children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers.

GREEN SOCIAL LABORATORIES

Three green social laboratories (i.e., "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina") were held by local elders and producers to transfer to adolescents, children, and interested citizens their knowledge on:

- the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana".

In these laboratories, the first, second, and third phases (i.e., concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization) of the learning by doing approach were implemented. The laboratories started with the knowledge transfer of cultivation, cooking, and harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana" from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants were actively engaged in the activities, as illustrated in the photos provided in Del. 4.1.

SOCIAL4FOOD COMPETITION

A culinary challenge was held during the "fagiolina festival" involving 5 groups composed of participants in the green social laboratories who tried their hand at cooking typical recipes. In this competition, the last phase (i.e., active experimentation) of the learning by doing approach was implemented. Participants were actively engaged in the activities, as illustrated in the photos provided in Del. 4.1.

SECOND STEP OF THE CO-DESIGN OF THE SOCIAL FARM

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th 2022, each participant was asked to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm (i.e people to be involved, tasks to perform, etc.). Through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm has been provided. Moreover, a group of "Fagiolina Ambassadors" has been

appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) have been selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.

Activity A5 – Evaluation, lessons learnt: the activity starts at month 4.

Activity A6 – Dissemination and communication: the D&C plan has been defined, the Website of the project has been implemented (<https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en>) and social media are available (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222>; <https://twitter.com/Social4foodP>)

2.2. Methodology of the engagement with local stakeholders

For the engagement of local stakeholders, a co-creation methodology has been defined for stimulating the transgenerational dialogue and establishing a process of contamination, inspiration, and sharing of ideas.

The co-creation methodology is based on the design thinking approach which is a non-linear, iterative process that provides a solution-based approach to solving problems. The design thinking approach is extremely useful when used to tackle complex problems and it serves to understand the human needs involved, reframe the problem in human-centric ways, create numerous ideas in brainstorming sessions, and adopt a hands-on approach to prototyping and testing. The approach, proposed by the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford (2019), is composed of five stages:

- Empathize: research users' needs
- Define: state users' needs and problems
- Ideate: challenge assumptions and create ideas
- Prototype: start to create solutions
- Test: try your solutions out

The five stages of the design thinking approach have been applied during the events planned within the project, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The design thinking approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

2.2.1. Emphasize and define

The first stage (emphasize and define) is applied during the Open day event, in which local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers are involved in the (i) storytelling of experiences on the growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana" and (ii) elicitation of ideas.

Specifically, two different sessions are organized to meet the needs of the different target groups: the former for adults and adolescents and the latter for children.

2.2.1.1. SESSION for ADULTS and ADOLESCENTS

In the first session, dedicated to adults and adolescents, the world café method is applied consisting of the following activities: collection of experiences, elicitation of ideas, sharing of ideas, and voting of ideas.

Collection of experiences

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their experiences:

- 1) What is your most significant experience in the GROWING of the "fagiolina arsolana" (or in the growing of agricultural products in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?

2) What is your most significant experience in the COOKING of the “fagiolina arsolana” (or of the typical cuisine of Arsoli in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?

Different groups of participants are formed, taking care to include at least one member of each target user for each group: adult, adolescent, man, and woman.

Each person has a maximum of 3 minutes available to tell their experience. After 20 minutes, each participant has 10 minutes to write a brief description of the experience (2-3 sentences), positive aspects, and the encountered difficulties on three post-its. The post-its are attached to a poster for the final discussion.

Elicitation of ideas

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

- 1) How to pass on the experience and skills necessary for the traditional growing and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana” from local elders to adolescents?
- 2) How to stimulate the involvement of local teenagers (including young immigrants) in the collaborative growing and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”?
- 3) How would you like to organize the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?

The different groups of participants appoint a spokesperson who illustrates the emerging ideas and a secretary who reports the ideas, on a sheet.

The group has a maximum of 10 minutes available for discussing and proposing ideas by answering the 3 triggering questions.

Sharing of ideas

The post-it containing the different ideas that emerged from the group’s discussion is put on a poster and the spokesperson of each group explains the ideas that emerged for each question.

Voting of ideas

Each participant is provided with 6 stickers to apply to the 2 ideas that he/she considers most relevant for each question (according to the level of appreciation). At the end of the vote, the most significant ideas are summarized.

2.2.1.2. SESSION for CHILDREN

In the second section, dedicated to children, the storytelling method is applied consisting of the following activities: storytelling of experiences with emotion definition, collection of tips, and drawings.

Storytelling of experiences

Two rounds of storytelling are organized: the former for the experiences in the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana” and the latter for its cooking.

In the first round, participants are divided into 3 groups; they are asked to tell their experience with the growing of garden products (in particular the “fagiolina arsolana”) to the other group members. Some possible examples are given (I sowed vegetables with my father/grandfather, I attended the bean harvest event, I sowed seedlings with my teachers, etc.). After the storytelling, participants are asked to write 1-2 sentences to describe their experience. Finally, each participant is provided with 5 stickers representing smiles with emotions (very happy, happy, indifferent, sad, and very sad) and is asked to apply them to the written experience (according to their level of satisfaction).

In the second round, the same process is followed focusing on the experiences in the cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”.

Collection of tips

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

- 1) What would you like to do to learn how to grow the “fagiolina arsolana”?
- 2) What would you like to do to learn how to cook the “fagiolina arsolana”?

Some possible examples are given (e.g., cultivating a vegetable garden with my companions, making a laboratory to learn, listening to the stories experienced by the elderly, etc.).

Drawings

Each participant is asked to realize a drawing for representing his/her experience.

2.2.2. Ideate

The second stage (ideate) is applied during the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD competition, and co-creation of the social farm), in which local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers are involved in.

During the green social laboratories and SOCIAL4FOOD competition the “learning by doing” is applied, which is an educational approach expounded by Paulo Freire (1982). It is a hands-on learning approach in which participants interact with their environment and actually “do” the activity to adapt and learn. The learning by doing approach is composed of the following four phases, as defined by Kolb (1984): (1) having a concrete experience followed by (2) observation of and reflection on that experience which leads to (3) the formation of abstract concepts (analysis) and generalizations (conclusions) which are then (4) used to test a hypothesis in future situations, resulting in new experiences.

The four phases of the learning-by-doing approach applied in the project are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The learning by doing approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

A brief description of each phase is provided below.

Concrete experience

This activity starts with the knowledge transfer of cultivation techniques/cooking recipes of the “fagiolina arsolana” from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants learn about the experience told by elderly and local farmers watching them in action. To acquire new knowledge, participants are actively engaged in cultivation/cooking activities.

Reflective observation

This phase in the learning cycle allows participants to discuss the experience with others. Communication at this stage is vital, as it allows participants to identify any discrepancies between their understanding and the experience itself. Participants are divided into groups and are invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties and the necessary improvements in the acquired knowledge.

Abstract conceptualization

In this phase, participants move from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They are asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes).

Active Experimentation

This phase in the cycle is the testing stage. Participants have a new cultivation/cooking experience in which they apply the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience phase (written in their experience notes).

2.2.2.1. GREEN SOCIAL LABORATORIES

Three different green social laboratories (i.e., "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina") are organized by local elders and producers to transfer to adolescents, children, and interested citizens their knowledge on:

- the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana".

In these laboratories, the first, second, and third phases (i.e., concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization) of the learning by doing approach are implemented.

2.2.2.2. SOCIAL4FOOD COMPETITION

A culinary challenge among different groups composed of participants in the green social laboratories is organized during the "fagiolina festival". Participants try their hand at cooking typical recipes by applying the concepts and knowledge acquired during the culinary laboratory.

In this competition, the last phase (i.e., active experimentation) of the learning-by-doing approach is implemented.

2.2.2.3. CO-CREATION OF THE SOCIAL FARM

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th 2022, each participant is asked to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm (e.g. people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.). Through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm is provided. Moreover, a group of "Fagiolina Ambassadors" is appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) are selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.

2.2.3. Prototype

The third stage (prototype) is applied during the Social farm Day in which the shared solution about the organization of the social farm (people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.) is illustrated to the audience. Afterward, according to the proposed organization of the social

farm, the “Fagiolina Ambassadors” and target participants are involved in the deforestation activities and preparation of common land for the sowing of the “fagiolina arsolana”.

2.2.4. Testing

During the last stage (testing) of the design thinking approach, a qualitative survey (questionnaires and interviews) for acquiring feedback from participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities is administered.

2.3. Work plan of the activities

The following table summarizes the activities planned in the work plan, and the expected and achieved outputs.

Activity	Description	Duration	Expected outputs/deliverables	Achieved Outputs
A1. Management	Financial, administrative, and technical management; data management plan (DMP)	M1 – M5	EO1.1 Project reports, EO1.2 DMP Del.1.1: DMP (M1) Del.1.2: Intermediate report (M3) Del.1.3: Final report (M5)	- Definition of the DMP (Del.1.1) - Intermediate report (Del.1.2)
A2. Target groups identification, need analysis	2.1 Call for participation: target groups identification 2.2 Open day event: needs analysis and ideas elicitation	M1	EO2.1 List of participants EO2.2 List of needs and ideas Del.2.1: Call for participation (M1) Del.2.2: Results of the Open day event (M1)	- Definition of the call for participation (Del.2.1) - Open day event organized and first step of the co-creation of the social farm for the extraction of needs and ideas performed (Del.2.2)
A3. Co-creation methodology definition	3.1 Definition of the co-creation strategy, planning of activities	M1	EO3.1 Plan of the co-creation activities Del.3.1: Co-creation strategy (M1)	- Definition of the co-creation methodology (Del.3.1)

<p>A4. SOCIAL4FOOD D training activities setting up, implementati on</p>	<p>4.1 Setting up of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities 4.2 Green social laboratories 4.3 SOCIAL4FOOD competition 4.4 Co-creation of the social farm</p>	<p>M2-M4</p>	<p>EO4.1 Green social laboratories (M4) EO4.2 SOCIAL4FOOD competition (M4) EO4.3 social farm co-designed (M4) Del.4.1: Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (M4)</p>	<p>- Green social laboratories organized - SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized - second step of the co-design of the social farm</p>
<p>A5. Evaluation, lessons learnt</p>	<p>5.1 Results Analysis and evaluation: Qualitative survey for feedback and possible refinements 5.2 Lessons learnt identification</p>	<p>M4-M5</p>	<p>EO5.1 List of feedback and necessary refinements (M5) EO5.2 Set out of Lessons learnt (M5) Del.5.1: Results of Qualitative survey (M5) Del.5.2: Lessons learnt (M5)</p>	<p>----</p>
<p>A6. Disseminatio n and communicati on</p>	<p>6.1 Definition of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) plan 6.2 Final outreach event for the general public; website and social media 6.3 1 Scientific publications</p>	<p>M1-M5</p>	<p>EO6.1 D&C plan (M1) EO6.2 Website and social media (M1) EO6.3 Final outreach event (M5) EO6.4 1 scientific article (M5)</p>	<p>- Website and social media available (https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en; https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222; https://twitter.com/Social4foodP) - Definition of the D&C plan</p>

2.4. Achievement of the objectives

The project defined three specific objectives and related expected outcomes described in the following table. The current level of achievement of the specific objectives is provided in the last column of the table.

Specific Objectives (SO)	Expected Outcomes (EO)	Measurements/Target value	Current value

<p><i>SO1: Engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities</i></p>	<p><i>EO1: Participation of local teenagers, children, and the interested citizens in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities taught by local elders and farmers (realised in Activity A2 and A4, del. 2.2 and 4.1)</i></p>	<p><i>- Number of local citizens involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities > 70 (10 teenagers, 40 children (9-12 years), 10 elders, and 10 citizens)</i></p>	<p><i>The total number of citizens and key stakeholders involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities organized in July, August, and September 2022 is 116. Specifically, 3 teenagers, 38 children, 13 elders, 55 citizens, and 7 local farmers.</i></p>
<p><i>SO2: Re-purposing of abandoned green spaces</i></p>	<p><i>EO2: Realisation of an inclusive and sustainable social farm (realised in Activity A4, del. 4.1)</i></p>	<p><i>- 1 vegetable garden for the growth of the "fagiolina" - 1 information stand with brochures illustrating the high quality of the "fagiolina"</i></p>	<p><i>Not achieved yet. The activity of co-creation of the social farm started on September 24th, 2022 and ends at the end of October.</i></p>
<p><i>SO3: Experimenting with a citizen engagement strategy to promote the culture and knowledge of typical local foods and traditional agricultural knowledge for replicating it in other similar contexts</i></p>	<p><i>EO3: Co-creation methodology to design the social farm, lessons learnt (realised in Activity A3 and A5, del. 3.1 and 5.2)</i></p>	<p><i>- Number of participants in the co-design process > 80</i></p>	<p><i>The citizen engagement strategy defined in Del.3.1 allowed to achieve a current number of participants in the co-design process equal to 116. Since the SO3 is not concluded yet the number of participants could increase.</i></p>

Therefore, SO1 and SO3 have been achieved. Indeed, the number of participants involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities and the co-design process is greater than the target values (i.e 70 people for SO1 and 80 people for SO3). Although the achieved number of participants is higher than the threshold (116 people involved), it is important to highlight that, the SO1 target values for the specific target groups have been only partially achieved

since the number of teenagers and children involved is less than the target value (3 teenagers have been involved instead of 10, and 38 children instead of 40).

To mitigate the risk of low teenager and children participation, a greater dissemination of the activities of the project in the middle schools will be carried out.

3. Outputs and outcomes of the Project

3.1. Identification and prioritization of challenges

The activities implemented within the SOCIAL4FOOD project in the first quarter contributed to the achievement of the expected impacts of the challenge “Re-connecting with nature” in the following ways:

Expected Impact 1: co-design of a social farm for re-purposing an abandoned green space and improving the aesthetics of the territory and the quality of life of the local community.

Expected Impact 2: implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities to promote the interaction and collaboration between different social groups

In the following table, the KPIs defined for assessing the achievement of these impacts and the current value of the KPIs achieved in the first quarter are illustrated.

<i>Expected IMPACTS</i>	<i>KPIs- target value</i>	<i>Current value</i>
Expected Impact 1	N° of local citizens and stakeholders involved in the process > 70 Citizen satisfaction degree > 70%, evaluated using a qualitative survey	The local citizens and stakeholders involved in the co-design of the social farm were 116. Citizen satisfaction degree is not assessed yet because the evaluation activity will be performed in October and November.
Expected Impact 2	N° of social groups involved > 3	The social groups involved in the implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities were the following five: teenagers, children (9-12 years), elders, citizens, and farmers.

Therefore, EO1 and EO2 have been achieved. Indeed, the current values of the KPIs are greater than the target values (i.e 70 people for EO1 and 3 target groups for EO2).

3.2. Ideation process to co-create solutions for the most pressing challenges

To co-create the social farm for re-purposing an abandoned green space and improving the aesthetics of the territory and quality of life of the local community, an ideation process based on the design thinking approach has been followed. A detailed description of the followed approach is provided in Section 2.2 and Deliverable 3.1.

3.3. Achievement of the outputs, compliance with the Application Form

The project defined several expected outputs for each activity planned in the application form. In the following table, the expected outputs and the achieved outputs are illustrated.

Expected outputs/deliverables	Achieved Outputs
<p>EO1.1 Project reports, EO1.2 DMP Del.1.1: DMP (M1) Del.1.2: Intermediate report (M3) Del.1.3: Final report (M5)</p>	<p>- Definition of the DMP (Del.1.1) - Intermediate report (Del.1.2)</p>
<p>EO2.1 List of participants EO2.2 List of needs and ideas Del.2.1: Call for participation (M1) Del.2.2: Results of the Open day event (M1)</p>	<p>- Definition of the call for participation (Del.2.1) - Open day event organized and first step of the co-creation of the social farm for the extraction of needs and ideas performed (Del.2.2)</p>
<p>EO3.1 Plan of the co-creation activities Del.3.1: Co-creation strategy (M1)</p>	<p>- Definition of the co-creation methodology (Del.3.1)</p>
<p>EO4.1 Green social laboratories (M4) EO4.2 SOCIAL4FOOD competition (M4) EO4.3 social farm co-designed (M4) Del.4.1: Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (M4)</p>	<p>- Green social laboratories organized - SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized - Second step of the co-design of the social farm</p>
<p>EO5.1 List of feedback and necessary refinements (M5) EO5.2 Set out of Lessons learnt (M5) Del.5.1: Results of Qualitative survey (M5) Del.5.2: Lessons learnt (M5)</p>	<p>Not achieved yet. The activities of results analysis and evaluation, and lessons learnt identification will start in October 2022.</p>
<p>EO6.1 D&C plan (M1) EO6.2 Website and social media (M1) EO6.3 Final outreach event (M5) EO6.4 1 scientific article (M5)</p>	<p>- Website and social media available (https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en; https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222; https://twitter.com/Social4foodP) - Definition of the D&C plan</p>

3.4. Impact of the activity

The activity carried out in the first quarter had a great social impact. In particular, the engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in both the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities and the co-design of the social farm allowed the Arsoli community to build a transgenerational dialogue and establish a process of productive contamination, inspiration, and shared ideas between older and younger generations.

The SOCIAL4FOOD training activities, and in particular the green social laboratories, also allowed to stimulate the reconnection between people and the natural environment by stimulating physical and psychological wellbeing. Moreover, they fostered social relationships and the aggregation opportunity, dramatically reduced by the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic and the widespread use of smartphones and other digital technologies that lead people to detach themselves from nature.

Another great social impact of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities was the maintenance and recovery of the traditional agricultural knowledge and the sustainable practices of the “fagiolina” production through the knowledge transfer of the typical recipes of the “fagiolina” and the experiences and skills needed for its growth.

4. Conclusion, lessons learnt and recommendations

4.1. Overall management process and risk mitigation

The timing of the activities is in line with the proposed work plan.

All the planned deliverables have been completed and submitted.

All the intermediate outcomes have been achieved. Specifically, the total number of citizens and key stakeholders involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities is more than 70 and the total number of participants in the co-design process is more than 80. More in detail, considering the KPIs defined in the Application form for each target group, all the thresholds have been satisfied, except for the adolescent target group. Specifically, the following target group participated in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities: 38 children instead of 40, 3 teenagers instead of 10, 55 citizens instead of 10, and 20 elders instead of 10 (of which 7 farmers). The number of teenagers and children to be involved is not yet achieved.

To mitigate the risk of low teenager and children participation, greater dissemination of the activities of the project in the middle schools will be carried out.

4.2. Recommendations for the replication and/or upscaling up of the realized activity

The following recommendations for the replication and/or upscaling up of the realized activity resulted from the current results:

- Dissemination and training activities should be performed in months M4-M5 to transfer the co-creation methodology to the municipalities of the neighboring towns in order to stimulate the transgenerational knowledge transfer and production of their typical local food;
- Involvement of the “Fagiolina Ambassadors”, the association of local farmers (“Amici della Fagiolina di Arsoli”), which aims at protecting and promoting the culture of the

"fagiolina", the Pro Loco, and the Senior citizen Center in the maintenance of the social farm and the re-implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities in the coming years.

5. Annexes

5.1. Evidences that describe the achievement of KPIs²:

5.1.1. Summary of good practices and lessons learnt (EITHE 14.1)

One best practice has been defined, which is the co-creation methodology (Activity 3), which will be validated and refined at month 5 according to the results of the qualitative survey.

Lessons learnt from the implementation and follow-up of the co-creation methodology during the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities will be identified and codified according to the results of the qualitative survey that is planned at month 5.

5.1.2. Dissemination of lessons learnt (EITHE 15.1)

Dissemination of the Open Day event and SOCIAL4FOOD training activities has been performed through the project website, the social media accounts dedicated to the project (Facebook and Twitter), and printed calls for participation in the project events.

5.1.2.1. *Illustrate the implementation of the project with pictures/graphic/image/ infographics – A picture is worth a thousand words! It is highly recommended to make efficient use of pictures/graphic/image/ infographics in social medial or any other channel.*

Some photos of the Open Day event organized on July 29th, 2022

Presentation of the SOCIAL4FOOD activities - adults and adolescents' session

² Please fill in the contribution table including all of the mandatory Core EIT KPIs in chapter 5.3

First step of the co-creation of the social farm (Collection of experiences and elicitation of ideas) - adults and adolescents' session

Sharing of ideas - adults and adolescents' session

Voting of ideas – adults and adolescents' session

Storytelling of experiences – children session

Collection of tips - children session

Drawings – children session

Some photos of the social laboratories organized on August 18th, 2022 and September 24th, 2022

Laboratory "I learn how to grow the fagiolina"

Land preparation

Sowing

Covering the seeds

Building of the “conocchie” (support scaffold for the growth of the plant)

Reflective Observation

Abstract Conceptualization

- ARATURA
 - FRESATURA
 - SOLCATURA (distanza 100 cm da un sodo e l'altro) usare TOPPA
 - X SOLCHI dritti → PALI CON FILO
 - SEMINA → TUBO DI PASTICA dove si SEMINANO I FAGIOLI stando in piedi: se ne piantano 5 a distanza di 40-50 cm di distanza. Fagioli ricoperti con la terra.
 - SARCHIATURA = ZAPPARE LA PIANTA e creare canale di irrigazione
 - "CONOCCHIATURA": si creano le CANNE come sostegno x la PIANTA che si ARRABBIATA con le CORDE
 - INNAFFIATURA → IN BASE AL TERRENO
 - RACCOLTA = LA FAGIOLINA e' SECCA

DIFFICOLTA'

- UTILIZZO SAPPA
 - FATICA FISICA

ASPETTI POSITIVI
 IMPARARE LA CULTURA ARABOLANA E A USARE GLI ATTREZZI AGRICOLI

DIARIO di VIAGGIO di CAMILLA

ARATURA DEL TERRENO
 - FRESATURA DEL TERRENO
 - SOLCATURA (distanza 60 cm)
 SOLCO FATTO CON CANNUCCE, FILO E ZAPPA
 PER PIANTE I FAGIOLI ABBIAMO USATO UN TUBO PER NON CURVARCI. (SEMINA) IN OGNI BUCIA CIRCA 5 FAGIOLI.
 SOLCO PROFONDO 10 CM.
 I SEMI VENGONO RICOPERTI CON LA TERRA.
 SI ASPETTA CHE LA PIANTINA CRESCA UN PO' SENZA FARE LE CORDE (SARCHIATURA) = ZAPPARE LA PIANTINA. VIENE CREATO IL CANALE PER FAR SCORRERE L'ACQUA
 - CONOCCHIATURA = 4 PALI ATTACCATI TRA LORO PER FAR CRESCERE LE CORDE DELLA PIANTA

DIFFICOLTA' INFILARE LE CANNE NEL TERRENO

FATICA FISICA C'ERA TROPPO SOLE PERCIO' HO SOFFERTO TANTISSIMO

ASPETTI POSITIVI STARE NELLA NATURA ED AVERE IMPARATO UNA NUOVA CULTURA

DIARIO DI VIAGGIO
 DI :

ARATURA TERRENO
 - FRESATURA TERRENO
 - SOLCATURA dis. 60 CM
 - PER FARE IL SOLCO DRITTO ABBIAMO USATO LA ZAPPA
 + SEMINA: SI PRENDE UN TUBO CHE SERVE A SEMINARE I FAGIOLI SENZA FARE LE CORDE. SE NE PIANTE 5 A DISTANZA DI 40 o 50 CM.
 - RICOPERTA DEI SEMI CON LA TERRA SCANATA
 - "SARCHIATURA": E' ZAPPARE LA PIANTA A CREARE IL CANALE PER L'IRRIGAZIONE
 - "CONOCCHIATURA": LE "CONOCCHIE" SONO DEL CANNE CHE SERVONO PER FAR CRESCERE E FAR ARRABBIARE LA FAGIOLINA
DIFFICOLTA': METTERE LE CANNE

Laboratory "I learn how to cook the fagiolina"

Preparation of the sauce

Preparation of the hand-made pasta

Final baking

Reflective Observation

Abstract Conceptualization

Laboratory "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina"

Concrete Experience

Reflective Observation

Abstract Conceptualization

Some photos of the SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized on September 4th, 2022

Some photos of the second step of the co-design of the social farm organized on September 24th, 2022.

Presentation of the results of first step of the co-creation activities

Collection of possible solutions

Collaborative discussion and definition of a shared solution

“Fagiolina Ambassadors” appointment

5.1.3. Dissemination and communication activities and number of people in these activities (EITHE 17.1)

The dissemination and communication activities of the project that are currently implemented are the project website and the social media accounts (Facebook and Twitter). The number of people currently reached through these activities is: 22 people from the project website, 58 people joined the SOCIAL4FOOD Facebook group, and 5 followers of the Twitter account.

The Final outreach event will be organized in month 5.

The communication material (brochure, short video, and scientific publication) will be provided in months 4 and 5.

5.1.3.1. Attendance sheets; the list of participants of each Citizen Engagement activities, events, workshops, etc.,

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the Open Day event organized on July 29th, 2022

Nome	Cognome	ETA	Firma
MARIA	LOTTI	71	Maria L. Lotti
ROBERTO	PUCCINI	68	Rob. Puccini
FILIPPO	CHITI	54	Filippo Chiti
ALBERTO	TARQUINI	83	Alberto Tarquini
PIETRO	CERRONI	54	Pietro Cerroni
VALENTINA	ZUCCHINI	34	Valentina Zucchini
TOMMASO	CERRONI	15	Tommaso Cerroni
MARCO	DI NARDO	15	Marco Di Nardo
ANGELO	BERNARDINI	21	Angelo Bernardini
DORJA	DI LILLO	66	Dorja Di Lillo
PIERLUIGI	ZITTO	64	Pierluigi Zitto
PIERLUIGI	DOZZA	28	Pierluigi Dozza
ALESSANDRO	AMICI	21	Alessandro Amici
NAPOLIONE	MARINO	75	Napoli Marini
GIUSEPPE	CAVALLI	48	Giuseppe Cavalli
PAOLO	NAPOLITANO	56	Paolo Napolitano
SYRIA	ALIMONTI	19	Syria Alimonti
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	Marco Proietti
DORINDA	D'OUZIA	17	Dorinda D'Ouzia
CLAUDIA	GREGORI	29	Claudia Gregori
BEATRICE MARIA	DE SANTIS	20	Beatrice Maria De Santis
CHIARA	BONNI	42	Chiara Bonni

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
GINEVRA	MASTRECCHIA	9
ROBERTO	MASI	8
JAMUELE	DE SORGI	10
DAVIDE	BAIACCO	12
ROCCO	ALFOUSO	10
VALENTINA	NAPOLEONI	8
CRISTIAN	PROIETTI	12
CECILIA	//	8
CAMILLA	MASI	10
MARCO	PROIETTI	11
CAMILLA	CAUCCI	12
LUDOVICO	CAUCCI	9
UTTOLOA	BERGAMASCHI	11
CARLOTTA	//	8
DAMIANO	MAGRAM	8
GINEVRA	LAURETTI	10

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of social laboratories organized on August 18th, 2022

Participants in the laboratory: the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana"

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022				
NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
VALENTINA	CALABARA	36	Valentina Calabara	valentina.calabara@gmail.com
EUGENIA	ALIMONTI	55	Eugenia Alimonti	eugenialimonti@gmail.com
BENEDETTA	TUZZA	71	Benedetta Tuzza	
RITA	DI MARCO	67	Rita Di Marco	
DORJA	DI LILLO	66	Dorja Di Lillo	
CAROLINA	DI LILLO	13	Carolina Di Lillo	
MARIA LUIGIA	DI LILLO	21	Maria Luigia Di Lillo	
MARIA ANTONIETTA	MASI	75	Maria Antonietta Masi	
DECCA	DECCA	53	Decca Decca	
TAMARA	PASSERI	45	Tamara Passeri	
GIUSEPPE	NOZZI	64	Giuseppe Nozzi	
FRANCA	MINATI	20	Franca Minati	FRANCA.MINATI@GMAIL.COM
NICOLETTA	MINATI	32	Nicoletta Minati	NIC.MINATI@GMAIL.COM
VALENTINA	PASCALI	34	Valentina Pascali	valentina.pascali@gmail.com
ROLANDO	PASSERI	51	Rolando Passeri	
CAMILLA	TOMASI	46	Camilla Tomasi	CAMILLA.TOMASI@FIRMA.IT
SERENA	PROIETTI	39	Serena Proietti	
ALBERTO	TARQUINI	83	Alberto Tarquini	
GIOVANNA	TARQUINI	42	Giovanna Tarquini	
LAURA	ZUCCHINI	35	Laura Zucchini	
JUAN CARLOS	BURNIA	47	Juan Carlos Burnia	
PIACENTINI	BERNARDINI	72	Piacentini Bernardini	

OTTAVIA	ORTISI	36	Ottavia Ortisi	
ANNA MARIA	ZEPARDI	51	Anna Maria Zepardi	
GIULIA	D'ANTINI	28	Giulia D'Antini	
FEDERICA	COLAPANESSE	29	Federica Colapanesse	
DAMA	BONNI	53	Dama Bonni	
FRANCA	NOZZI	64	Franca Nozzi	
EUSA	DI GIUSEPPE	38	Eusa Di Giuseppe	
NATHASCHA	NARDONI	41	Nathascha Nardoni	
MARIO	NAPOLEONI	75	Mario Napoleoni	
MIRKO	LUPI	42	Mirko Lupi	
PAOLO	DE SANTIS	40	Paolo De Santis	
MARIA ANTONIETTA	MASI	76	Maria Antonietta Masi	
ERICA	PROIETTI	63	Erica Proietti	
DANIELA	MASI	43	Daniela Masi	
GIULIA	GIULI	60	Giulia Giuli	
VALENTINA	NAPOLEONI	39	Valentina Napoleoni	
MAURIZIO	NOZZI	50	Maurizio Nozzi	
LOREDANA	BURNIA	63	Loredana Burnia	
ANNA MARIA	RINELLI	65	Anna Maria Rinelli	
CHIARA	BONNI	42	Chiara Bonni	

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
ROBERTO	MASI	8
DAMIANO	HAGGAM	8
COSTANZA	BORGHI	7
ADELE	DESANTIS	3
LUCA	LUCCI	7
MARCO	//	5
FRANCESCO	PETRA	4
PABLO	D'ASCENZI	3,5
AURORA	BUCCHIA LUCCIANO	5
ECLA	//	6
CAMILLA	MASI	10
LORENZO	PASSARELLI	10
MATEO	LUPI	8
ANGELICA	CECCOM	6
MANUEL	DE ANGENS	6
NARLOONI	CARLOTTI	6
MARY	CATULLA	10
LUIGI	CAUCCI	8
GIUSEPPE	MASTRECCIA	9
OMERO	AMICI	8
MELISSA	PIACENTINI	6
PARIDE	FRIGUCCI	4

Participants in the laboratory: the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana"

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
DAMIANO	MASI	51	[Signature]	damiano.masi@gmail.com
CHIARA	BONNI	42	[Signature]	chiara.bonni@gmail.com
RODOLFO	PASSERI	51	[Signature]	
ROMINA	PURBANO	44	[Signature]	rominapurbano@gmail.com
ELISA	CHITI	43	[Signature]	elisa.chiti@gmail.com
NICOLETTA	SIMBOLI	40	[Signature]	nicolettasimboli@gmail.com
FRANCESCA	CENSI	40	[Signature]	francesca.censi@gmail.com
VALENTINA	PULICANI	34	[Signature]	valentina.pulicani@gmail.com
FABIO	DESANTIS	40	[Signature]	fabio.desantis@gmail.com
NICOLETTA	HINATI	32	[Signature]	nicolettahinati@gmail.com
PIETRO	CERRONI	54	[Signature]	pietro.cerroni@gmail.com
AUGUSTO	MASI	62	[Signature]	augusto.masi@gmail.com
PAURO	SPARDELLA	76	[Signature]	pauro.spardezza@gmail.com
FRANCESCO	GAN		[Signature]	francesco.gan@gmail.com
AMANDA	ZUCCHETTI	44	[Signature]	amanda.zucchetti@gmail.com
DAFNE	TARQUINI	51	[Signature]	dafne.tarquini@gmail.com
VITTORIO	PROIETTI	55	[Signature]	vittorio.proietti@gmail.com
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	[Signature]	marco.proietti@gmail.com

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
LUIGI	CAUCCI	9
CAMILLA	//	12
DARIO	AMICI	8
GIUSEPPE	MASTRECCIA	9
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
ADELE	DESANTIS	3
ROBERTO	MASI	8
TOMMASO	CERBONI	15

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized on September 4th, 2022

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 04 SETTEMBRE 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
NICOLETTA	MINATI	32	<i>Nicola Minati</i>	nic.minati@gmail.com
FABIO	DESANTIS	40	<i>Fabio Desantis</i>	DESANTISF35@gmail.com
CRISTINA	DI PROVO	30	<i>Crystina</i>	crystina.di.provo@gmail.com
CLAUDIA	GREGORI	29	<i>Claudia</i>	claudia.gregori@gmail.com
FEDERICA	CAMPARANESCHI	23	<i>Federica</i>	federica.camparaneschi@gmail.com
CARLETTA	CECCONI	28	<i>Carletta</i>	carletta.ceconi@gmail.com
FEDERICA	BONM	45	<i>Federica</i>	fedra.bonm@univ.it
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	<i>Marco</i>	proetti.marco@gmail.com
ARIANNA	CENUSI	46	<i>Arianna</i>	arianna.cenusi@gmail.com
FABRIZIO	CAUCCI	48	<i>Fabrizio</i>	caucci.fabrizio@gmail.com
ETILIA	COSTANTINI	40	<i>Etilia</i>	emilia.costantini@gmail.com
TAMARA	PASSERI	45	<i>Tamara</i>	
MARIO	D'UBARO	50	<i>Mario</i>	
VALENTINA	CINELLI	43	<i>Valentina</i>	

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 04 SETTEMBRE 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
ADELE	DESANTIS	3
GINEVRA	MASTRECCHIA	9
ALEXANDRA	CECONI	5
ROCCO	ALFONSI	11
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
CLOE	BRUM	11
CAMILLA	MASI	10
SAMUELE	DESOUKI	11
LORENZO	IASPARELLI	10
LEONARDO	PASSARELLI	12
GIULIA	TOSI	11
GIULIA	MASI	3
LUDOVICO	CAUCCI	9
DAMIANO	MAGGIARI	8

	ANDREA	D'UBARO	9
	ISABELLA	DI CENUSI	11
	GIULIA	DESOUKI	9
	UOLA	IACOBACCI	9
	MAYA	TARQUINI	12
	ANNA	IACOBACCI	6

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the laboratory: the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana" organized on September 24th, 2022.

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022

Laboratorio

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
SAURO	SPARDELLA	24	<i>Sauro</i>	SBASAVROB@gmail.com
MARIA	NAPOLITANI	75	<i>Maria</i>	maria.napolitano@gmail.com
PETRO	CERRONI	54	<i>Pietro</i>	petro.cerroni@gmail.com
VALENTINA	POUCANI	34	<i>Valentina</i>	valentina.poucani@gmail.com
ANNUNZIATA	ERCO	64	<i>Annunziata</i>	annunziata.ercio@gmail.com
AUGUSTO	MASI	60	<i>Augusto</i>	augusto.masi@gmail.com
MAURIZIO	AMICI	50	<i>Maurizio</i>	
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	<i>Marco</i>	proetti.marco@gmail.com

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022

Laboratorio

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
ROCCO	ALFONSI	11
TOMMASO	CERRONI	15
GINEVRA	MASTRECCHIA	9
DARIO	AMICI	8
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
MARCO	D'UBARO	15

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the second step of the co-design of the social farm organized on September 24th, 2022.

Second phase of the co-creation of the social farm

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022
Co-creazione dell'orto sociale

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
Valeria	Policam	60	<i>Valeria Policam</i>	
Valeria	POLICAM	34	<i>Valeria Policam</i>	
MARIO	AROLEOM	75	<i>Mario Aroleom</i>	
SAURO	SEMPRELLI	74	<i>Sauro Semprelli</i>	
ARGEO	MASI	61	<i>Argio Masi</i>	
FABRIZIO	PROIETTI	74	<i>Fabrizio Proietti</i>	
NETTO	CERFOM	54		
ROLANDO	PASSERA	51	<i>Rolando Passera</i>	
ANGELA	BERNARDINI	81	<i>Angela Bernardini</i>	
VALERIA	AROLEOM	39	<i>Valeria Aroleom</i>	
BEATRICE	BRUNI	47	<i>Beatrice Bruni</i>	
CECILIA	AMICI	79	<i>Cecilia Amici</i>	

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022
Co-creazione dell'orto sociale

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
CAMILIA	MASI	10
GIULIA	MARTELLA	9
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
DARIO	AMICI	8
ROCCO	ALFONSI	11
TOMMASO	CERFOM	15
MARCO	DI MARCO	15
GIULIA	TOSI	11
LORENZO	PASAPRELLI	10
DAMIANO	MARANI	8

5.2. Contribution to the mandatory Core EIT KPIs

KPI Code and name	KPI description	KPI Target value	Planned project contribution according to the Application Form	Real project contribution at the end of month 3 (September 2022)
EITHE 14.1 Good practices and lessons learnt identified and codified by the project.	Number of good practices ³ and lessons learnt ⁴ identified and codified by the project. Structured data: ✓ List incl. the type, title and short description	1	The project provides 1 best practice that is the co-creation methodology (Activity 3) and 1 Lessons learnt from the implementation and follow-up of the co-creation methodology during the SLOWFOOD training activities and the social farm	1 best practice defined, which is the co-creation methodology (Activity 3), which will be validated and refined at month 5 according to the results of the qualitative survey.
EITHE 15.1 Results, lessons learnt, and good practices disseminated by the project through appropriate means (e.g., publications, online repositories, fact sheets, targeted workshops etc.)	Number of results, good practices and lessons learnt disseminated Structured data: ✓ List incl. the type, title, List of the website links showing the dissemination	1	Results, good practices and lessons learnt disseminated through the following 4 means of communication: - the project website; - social media accounts dedicated to the project; - research article publication - final outreach event	Results disseminated through the following 2 means of communication: - the project website; - social media accounts dedicated to the project.

³ Good practice is a practice that has been proven to work well and produce good results and is therefore recommended as a model.

⁴ Lessons learnt are an analysis / record of a learning process in the development, implementation and follow-up of an innovative approach, process or activity. Lessons learnt are often a by-product of identifying and validating good practices

EITHE 17.1 Number of dissemination and communication activities of the project and number of people reached through these activities	Structured data:			
	✓ Physical or online event title and number of its participants	60	1 Physical Final outreach event (> 60 participants)	The Final outreach event will be organized at month 5.
	✓ Website/social media	1	1 Project website 1 Facebook account 1 Twitter account	1 Project website available at https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en ; 1 Facebook account available at https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222 ; 1 Twitter account available at https://twitter.com/Social4foodP
	✓ Disseminated/communication material	1	1 Research article 1 brochure 1 short video	Communication material will be provided at months 4 and 5.